

Minireview of Adverse Effects of Some Drugs Used in Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract

Several drugs have been used for treatment of Diabetes Mellitus such as sulfonylureas, biguanides, thiazolidines and others. The aim of this mini-review was to find some adverse effects produced by these drugs using both “pubmed” and “google scholar” as information sources. The results indicate that thiazolidinediones may produce higher adverse effects compared with the other hypoglycemic drugs.

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1. Introduction

One of the main problems worldwide is cardiovascular diseases. [1] There are data, which indicate that Diabetes Mellitus can be a risk factor for the development of this type of clinical pathologies [2, 3]. Diabetes Mellitus, it is characterized by changes in the production of insulin and alterations in the metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins and lipids [4]. Several clinical and epidemiological data indicate that in Mexico, it is the third cause of death in patients of 55 to 64 years old [5, 6].

It is important to mention, that there are several drugs for the treatment of diabetes such as sensitizers (biguanides, thiazolidinediones, Lyn Kinase activa-tors), secretagogues (sulfonylureas and non-sulfonylureas secretagogues), alpha-glucosidases inhibitors, peptides analogs, incretin mimetics, amylin analogues) and glycosurics. [7, 8]

The biological activity of these drugs can following different ways for lower blood sugar such as:

- Stimulating the pancreas to produce and release more insulin;
- Inhibiting the production and release of glucose from the liver;
- Inhibition of biological activity of some stomach enzymes that break down carbohydrates;
- Improving the sensitivity of cells to insulin;
- Inhibiting the reabsorption of glucose in the kidneys. However, some these oral drugs may induce some adverse effects, for example: Sulfonylureas, Biguanides, α -glucosidases inhibitors, Thiazolidinediones.

2. Oral drugs

2.1. Sulfonylureas

There are data which indicate that use of sulfonylureas is associated to adverse effect [9, 10] for example hypoglycemia [11-15] that can be profound and prolonged, mainly in patient's geriatric. In addition, it is important to mention that some data indicate that higher sulfonylureas levels could be a risk factor to development

cardiovascular diseases [16], In this sense, the sulfonylureas that can produce this phenomenon are chlorpropamide and glibenclamide which may exert severe hypoglycaemia, especially when the elimination of the drug is reduced by renal failure [17]. These data are supported by studies carried out in diabetic patients treated with sulfonylureas, which presented a higher death risk due to hypoglycaemia [13, 18-20]. Other reports indicate that the use of glibenclamide can cause intrahepatic cholestasis and skin bullas in diabetic patients of 60 years old [21, 22].

2.2. Biguanides

There are studies which indicate that biguanides can be accumulated in intestinal cells in higher concentrations compared with other tissues; this phenomenon could impair glucose utilization by suppressing the synthesis of ATP required for active absorption of glucose. In addition, the biguanides are associated with changes in lactate levels which may result in lactic acidosis. These drugs belonging to this group should be avoided in patients suffering from complications with renal failure, hepatic dysfunction and heart failure and hypoxemia situations, including myocardial ischemia and pulmonary insufficiency, issues in which tissue anoxia or altered cell metabolism favors the production of lactate [23-26].

On the other hand, a report showed that the administration of metformin to a 58-year-old male patient with diabetes produces metabolic acidosis and hypertension [24]. In addition, there are some reports which suggest that biguanides may exert gastrointestinal disorders, hypoglycaemia, poor absorption of vitamin B12 and folic acid [27-32]. Therefore, all biguanides should be avoided in patients with renal insufficiency, hepatic dysfunction and heart failure due to the possibility of an increase in metformin levels in the blood [33]

2.3. α -glucosidases inhibitors

These drugs have been associated with gastrointestinal adverse effects, predominantly flatulence, dyspepsia and diarrhea. However, it has been observed that these effects produced by acarbose are higher compared with the biological activity of miglitol. In addition, other data indicate that acarbose can produce dose-dependent liver

toxicity in diabetic patients [34-37]. It is noteworthy that acarbose the concurrent use with other hypoglycemic agents such as sulfonylureas and insulin may cause a greater frequency of hypoglycemia [38].

2.4. Thiazolidinediones

Some studies showed that monotherapy with thiazolidinediones can induce edema consequently bring as resulting an increase in biological activity of sympathetic nervous system, which may induce changes on interstitial ion transport and alterations in endothelial permeability [42, 44, 48, 50, 51, 53, 55, 57-59, 62-69]. In addition, there are several reports which indicate that use thiazolidinediones can increased weight body [8, 39- 61].

On the other hand, several studies showed that treatment for 12 days with rosiglitazone can induce heart failure in diabetic patients [40, 53-55, 57, 59, 63, 66, 70-79]. Also, other reports indicate that thiazolidinediones significant increase the risk of myocardial infarction and different cardiovascular events such as stroke, ischemia, ventricular arrhythmia [42, 44, 45, 47, 53, 55, 63, 66, 69, 75, 77, 80-89].

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, this minireview showed that several drugs have used for treatment of Diabetes Mellitus; however, the thiazolidinediones may produce higher adverse effects compared with the other oral hypoglycemic drugs.

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